

RESOLUTE
Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

Project number 777372

**WP2 – SLC Deorphanisation
 Process**

D2.2 Methodology for general detection of plasma metabolites and drug/dietary components.

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¹ Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

R = Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc.

² Please choose the appropriate reference and delete the rest:

PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web;

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CI = Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.

Description of Work	Version	Date
	V1.0	16 December 2019

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V0.1	06.12.2019	First Draft (MWM)
V0.2	10.12.2019	Inclusion of further details re data analysis (MWM)
V0.3	11.12.2019	Further details added regarding sample preparation and data analysis
V0.4	12.12.2019	Amendments to figures and text
V0.5	15.12.2019	Further amendments to text.
V1.0	16.12.2019	Final version.

Publishable Summary

Work package 2 aims to set up approaches to successfully deorphanize SLCs. At the core of the strategy is the use of genetically engineered cells and metabolomics to provide an understanding of substrate (and inhibitor) specificities of SLCs.

To achieve this goal, methodologies have been developed using untargeted LC-HRMS/MS analysis to enable the reliable detection of >3,000 individual compounds in human serum and cell extracts. These are broadly based on ³ and ⁴, and follow guidelines described in ⁵, with further details provided below. Using these methodologies enables the measurement of differences in uptake of a broad range of compounds present in serum by cell lines. Comparison of the uptake of serum compounds by genetically engineered cell lines, created by WP1 (wild-type, SLC knock-outs and overexpression), incubated in pooled human serum will provide clues as to the natural substrates of SLCs.

Methods

Sample preparation for LC-MS/MS analysis

Following incubation of cells in human serum, spent serum is collected after centrifugation, followed by extraction using methanol. The remaining cell pellet is washed with PBS (at 37 °C), followed by quenching and extraction of intracellular metabolites using 80 % methanol. The spent serum and intracellular extracts are subsequently lyophilised (with a mixture of internal standards spiked in prior to lyophilisation) and reconstituted in water ready for analysis by LC-HRMS/MS.

The above samples are taken at various time points over a 30-minute period to enable kinetics of the uptake of compounds to be measured from both cell and spent serum extracts. The number of time points assayed as well as the acquisition of both intra- and extracellular samples will depend on the orphan status of the SLC, whether the SLC is within the WP4 priority list and its cellular localisation. It is important to note that extracellular LC-MS/MS analysis is best suited to SLCs that localise to the plasma membrane, whilst intracellular located SLCs may be best studied using biochemical assays on isolated organelles.

For subsequent LC-MS/MS analysis of spent serum extracts, serum (without cell incubation) is used as the QC samples. This is a standard reference material that will be consistent across analytical runs as described in ⁵. The QC serum samples are prepared in the same way as spent serum samples.

As described below in Figure 1, sample preparation for untargeted metabolomics and the analyses of these will take place across multiple sites. Experiments (incubation of cells in serum) will take place at CeMM. These samples will then be sent to the University of Liverpool where samples will be prepared for LC-MS/MS analysis and then distributed for data acquisition by the University of Liverpool and Pfizer.

³ Dunn, W. B., et al. (2011). "Procedures for large-scale metabolic profiling of serum and plasma using gas chromatography and liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry." *Nat Protoc* **6**(7): 1060-1083.

⁴ Mullard, G., et al. (2015). "A new strategy for MS/MS data acquisition applying multiple data dependent experiments on Orbitrap mass spectrometers in non-targeted metabolomic applications." *Metabolomics* **11**(5): 1068-1080.

⁵ Broadhurst, D., et al. (2018). "Guidelines and considerations for the use of system suitability and quality control samples in mass spectrometry assays applied in untargeted clinical metabolomic studies." *Metabolomics* **14**(6): 72.

Figure 1. Workflow for untargeted metabolomics sample preparation and analysis in WP2 Task 2.2

Untargeted LC-HRMS/MS

Various parameters have been optimised to maximise the number and breadth of compounds detected and identified by LC-HRMS/MS. This includes:

- A reversed-phase chromatography elution profile using a C18 column.
- Optimised HESI source conditions for MS data acquisition using ThermoScientific QExactive Classic and QExactive Plus instruments.
- MS and data dependent MS2 acquisition parameters.
 - o MS2 acquisition includes fragmentation by HCD using various collision energies, as well as acquisition of data over various m/z ranges to maximise identification confidence, as described in⁴
- Acquisition sequence is performed as described in⁵ to include:
 - o System suitability blank injection (to assess and remove background/instrument contaminants), and system suitability injections (containing standards, to assess system performance) prior to commencing the analytical run.
 - o Conditioning QC samples.
 - o Extraction blanks.
 - o QC samples interspersed at regular intervals between randomised analytical samples.
- QC samples for spent serum analyses will utilise serum as a standard reference material, whereas for intracellular analyses, pooled samples will be prepared for this purpose.
- Replicates will consist of extraction replicates. This represents a necessary compromise (ideally replicates would consist of samples prepared on different experimental days) to ensure that as high throughput analysis can be performed with respect to the differential uptake of serum compounds by cell lines.

These settings enable the detection of ca 4,000 compounds in ESI+ and ca 2,000 compounds in ESI-.

Data preprocessing

Following data acquisition, the .RAW MS files are imported into Compound Discoverer 3.1 (CD3.1) software where data deconvolution is performed. Workflows have been put together to enable this to be performed efficiently in CD3.1 as shown in Figure 2. After importing the data into CD3.1, samples are assigned as blanks, QCs, samples (including grouping) and samples for identification (pooled samples where ddMS is performed). The workflow, as shown in Figure 2 performs all the necessary steps for alignment of retention times, spectral annotation and identification, and normalisation. Annotation and identification is performed by assigning spectra to given predicted compositions, as well as comparison to mass and spectral libraries such as ChemSpider, mzCloud or user defined and acquired libraries.

Alternatively, data preprocessing can occur in El Maven, an open source mass spectrometry software, creating a similar output to CD3.1.

Figure 2. Compound Discoverer 3.1 Untargeted Metabolomics Workflow

Data analysis and visualisation

The output of the preprocessing performed in CD3.1 is exported as a .xlsx file containing the detected compounds against the peak areas in the various samples analysed. This is subsequently imported into a KNIME workflow to perform normalisation, statistical analysis and visualisation of the results. These analyses include descriptive statistics, as well as calculation of fold changes and significance of these using statistical tests such as ANOVA, as well as a number of strategies to avoid false discoveries as described in ⁶. Visualisation is performed in the form of appropriate charts such as box plots including individual data points, volcano plots, and principal component analysis plots. Additionally, Upset^{7,8} plots are utilised to look at common and unique compounds between cell lines.

Alternatively, data analysis and visualisation is also possible using Polly MetScape software from Elucidata.

Conclusion

Robust protocols for the detection of serum metabolites and supplemented chemicals such as drugs or diet derived compounds have been developed.

Repository for primary data

Raw MS data files will be uploaded to the RESOLUTE server based at CeMM in their original format (.RAW). In addition, processed data will be uploaded to the RESOLUTE data base. Once data is released from the consortium to the public as described in the dissemination and exploitation plan (D9.2) and data management plan (D8.1), raw and processed data as well as sample and experiment metadata will be uploaded to public repositories such as Metabolights.

⁶ Broadhurst, D.I., Kell, D.B. Statistical strategies for avoiding false discoveries in metabolomics and related experiments. *Metabolomics* **2**, 171–196 (2006) doi:10.1007/s11306-006-0037-z

⁷ Lex, A., et al. (2014). "UpSet: Visualization of Intersecting Sets." *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics* **20**(12): 1983-1992.

⁸ Conway, J. R., et al. (2017). "UpSetR: an R package for the visualization of intersecting sets and their properties." *Bioinformatics* **33**(18): 2938-2940.